

FIBRE/MATRIX INTERFACE TESTING USING THE SINGLE FIBRE BROUTMAN TEST

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SUMMARY: The single fibre Broutman test was selected for investigating the fibre/matrix interface debonding behaviour when subjected to a transverse tensile stress. PAN-based carbon fibres having different surface finishes and glass fibres were embedded in epoxy and/or polyester resins and tested. During testing, damage was detected using visual observation and Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring. AE failure mechanism separation was based on parameters from the time-amplitude domain (event width and amplitude) and on Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) frequency spectra. Stresses in the specimens were evaluated using a two dimensional Finite Element Model (FEM). Two failure mechanisms appeared to be in competition in the Broutman test: (a) fibre compressive fragmentation, characteristic of the shear properties of the interface, and (b) fibre/matrix interface debonding under transverse tensile stresses, characteristic of the transverse properties of the interface. Thermal residual stresses were investigated and a FEM simulation showed that they encouraged fibre compressive fragmentation.

KEYWORDS: Broutman Test, Fibre/Matrix Interface, Transverse Debonding, Compressive Fragmentation, Acoustic Emission.

INTRODUCTION

Most common testing procedures associated with fibre/matrix interface characterisation aim at determining the interfacial shear strength. These methods, reviewed by Herrera-Franco and Drzal [1], include single fibre tests (Single Fibre Pull-Out Test, Microdebonding Test, Fragmentation Test, Microindentation Test) and bulk composite tests (Iosipescu Shear Test, Short Beam Shear Test). The limitations of shear characterisation of the interface were outlined recently [2], as different interface characteristics are involved depending on the load mixity (mode I/mode II ratio) during failure of the interface. Moreover, in shear testing, the results obtained by any available test, are always the sum of a bonding component (actual bonding of the matrix onto the fibre) and a friction component (friction between fibre and matrix due to fibre roughness), the latter is not directly related to adhesion [3]. By creating a debonding due to transverse stresses, the friction component is not present and the results would characterise more closely the fibre/matrix adhesion. Transverse bulk composite testing, i.e. transverse tensile and transverse three-point bending tests, performed on carbon fibre reinforced epoxy systems illustrated the strong effect of fibre/matrix adhesion on the composite transverse properties [4, 5]. In micro-composite tests (single fibre tests), failure can be better controlled than in macro-composite tests (bulk composite tests), and, also, fracture mechanisms can be isolated [6]. Therefore, it is of interest to characterise the fibre/matrix interface transverse properties using a micro-composite test procedure, in particular to study the transverse debonding phenomenon.

EXPERIMENTAL AND MODELLING

The Broutman test is based on the compression of a necked shape specimen in which a single fibre is laid longitudinally as shown in Fig. 1. The application of a compressive load to the necked shape specimen results in large compressive stresses, σ_y , in the smallest cross section which in turn cause Poisson's expansion in the transverse direction. As the Poisson's ratio of the matrix is larger than that of the fibre, the transverse expansion of the matrix is larger than that of the fibre and a transverse debonding stress is induced at the interface, σ^{Poisson} , which can be computed with the equation in Fig.1 [7]. In the X-direction, the transverse tensile stress, $\sigma_x^{\text{Poisson}}$, is countered by a transverse compression stress due to the neck geometry of the specimen; the resultant, σ_x^{global} , is tensile but lower in magnitude than the transverse tensile stress in the Z-direction, $\sigma_z^{\text{Poisson}}$ [8]. Therefore, debonding occurs in the Z-direction at the critical point where the transverse stress is maximum, and damage is not initiated at the fibre ends. Also, the X-axis symmetry of the specimen eliminates the shear stresses at the critical point.

The characterisation was performed on Tenax high tenacity PAN-based carbon fibres supplied by Akzo (Wuppertal, Germany), having received different surface treatments including: no treatment (the bare fibre, HTA5000), a standard oxydation treatment (HTA5001), a standard oxydation treatment with 0.15% antistatic agent coating (HTA5411) and a standard oxydation treatment with a 1.25% epoxy sizing (HTA5131). Also, a glass fibre, 80 μm in diameter, having received an aminosilane coating and provided by the Institute for Polymer Research, (Dresden, Germany) was used. Two epoxy resins, provided by Ciba-Geigy (Basel, Switzerland), were applied in the study, a hot curing system (LY556/HY917/DY070; 100:90:0.5) with a curing cycle of 10 hours at 90°C and a cold curing system (LY5052/HY5052; 100:38) cured for 24 hours at room temperature. A polyester resin was also used, and for transparency reasons, the UP resin Glasklar provided by R&B GmbH (Germany), was selected and cured with 1.5 wt% MEKP (Methyl Ethyl Ketone Peroxyd) for 24 hours at room temperature, followed by 24 hours at 60°C.

The Broutman test was performed in a universal testing machine (Zwick 1474) with crosshead speeds of 2 and 5 mm/min for GF and CF systems, respectively. Fibre breaking was detected using visual observation under linear transmitted polarised light (Fig. 2), while debonding was observed under incident normal light. Also, the Acoustic Emission (AE) activity was monitored throughout the test using a Defektophone NEZ 220 analyser recording the time parameters of the demodulated AE waveform (i.e. elapsed time since the beginning of the measurement, ringdown count, rise time, event width, peak amplitude, event number) and a Signalyser card (both equipment from Central Research Institute for Physics, Budapest, Hungary) recording the waveform of each individual AE event [9]. The frequency spectra of the AE records were obtained from the AE waveforms using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis.

In the X-Y plane, the stress distribution in the specimen was evaluated using a Finite Element Model (FEM) in static analysis; in the Z-direction, the Broutman equation (Fig. 1) was used for computing the transverse debonding stress, $\sigma_z^{\text{Poisson}}$. The FEM was verified by simulating photoelastic fringe patterns which were compared to experimental photoelastic fringe patterns obtained under monochromatic circularly polarised light [8]. The deformation problem was solved under axisymmetric conditions. In the X-Y plane, the specimen presents two axes of symmetry (X and Y-axes), therefore, only one quarter of the geometry was modelled. The fibre was meshed with 4-noded elements (3 elements in the fibre half-thickness) and the matrix with 3-noded elements, in order to accommodate the geometry requirements. The

typical mesh includes 12960 elements; this large number of elements, due to the small dimension of the fibre, guarantees reasonable aspect ratios. The fibre/matrix interface was assumed to be perfect, accordingly, all stress predictions obtained with the model are only valid before any interface damage has occurred. The simulation was performed on a GF/epoxy system, with a 80 μm fibre diameter; materials properties from [8] were used for modelling. The model was solved using a commercial FEA package ANSYS v5.4 running on a Power Indigo2 Silicone Graphics workstation fitted with a R10000 processor and 386 Mbytes RAM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two failure mechanisms appeared to be in competition in the Broutman test, i.e. (a) fibre breaking under compressive stresses (Fig. 3) and (b) fibre/matrix interface transverse debonding (Fig. 4). When the fibre/matrix interface bond strength is high (case (a)), as it was for PAN CF/epoxy (LY556/HY917/DY070) systems, fibre breaking happens first because the compressive stress in the fibre exceeds the fibre compressive strength before the transverse debonding stress exceeds the interfacial transverse strength. In this situation the results are interpreted as in a compressive fragmentation test, and the number of fibre breaks and the fragment lengths characterise the shear properties of the fibre/matrix interface (Fig 5). The number of fibre breaks was determined visually (Fig. 3-a) and from the AE records (Fig 6); in Fig. 5, the latter is lower than the actual number of breaks determined visually because some breaking events, very close together in time or simultaneous, are missed by the detection facility. Average fragment lengths as measured from Fig. 5, ranged from $146.1 \pm 18.9 \mu\text{m}$ for the epoxy sized fibre (HTA5131) to $393.3 \pm 42.6 \mu\text{m}$ for the bare fibre (HTA5000). These values are about one half of common fragment lengths reported with the tensile fragmentation test [4]. The determination of the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) from the compressive fragmentation data differs from common tensile fragmentation tests and requires to reconsider the matrix to fibre stress transfer profile [9]. Two approaches were adopted to determine the IFSS, in both cases the fibre compressive strength was assumed to be half of the tensile strength [10, 11]. In the first method, it was assumed that there is no stress transfer at the fragment ends, as in tensile fragmentation where all the stress transfer from matrix to fibre is attributed to interfacial shear stress [10]. This method, determining an upper bound for the interfacial shear strength, leads to values of 40.6 MPa and 29.3 MPa for the IFSS of HTA5131/epoxy and HTA5411/epoxy systems, respectively; they are in close agreement with the values reported from tensile fragmentation tests [4]. The second approach assumed no stress discontinuity at the break point, the stress in one fragment is fully transmitted to the adjacent fragment through the contact between two fragments (Fig. 3-b) [12]. The values determined under this assumption, corresponding to a lower bound of the IFSS, were 17.5 MPa and 15.1 MPa for the HTA5131/epoxy and HTA5411/epoxy systems, respectively.

Alternatively, when the interface adhesion quality is not so good (case (b)), interfacial debonding under transverse stresses happens first during the Broutman test, and results are characteristic of the transverse properties of the interface. Fibre/matrix interface debonding was observed for test specimens in which a 80 μm diameter glass fibre, coated with a release agent or not, was embedded in a polyester resin or in a cold curing epoxy resin (LY5052/HY5052). In Fig. 4-a, the debonding occurred in the middle of the specimen. In this specific case, debonding was only partial (not over the full fibre length), so that the undamaged interface could still transmit the load to the fibre leading subsequently to a fibre break (Fig. 7). Using a CCD camera mounted on a stereo-microscope [8], the progression of the debonding front was recorded as a function of the applied interfacial transverse stress. It revealed that the debonding process happened in a 'stop and start' mechanism (Fig. 8). The

interfacial transverse stresses at which debonding was initiated, $\sigma_z^{\text{Poisson}}$, were determined with the FEM and the Broutman equation (Fig. 1). They were of the order of 10 to 12 MPa for the GF/polyester and GF/epoxy (LY5052/HY5052) systems, being quite low in comparison to common values reported for GF/epoxy transverse strengths ranging from 30 to 50 MPa [4].

In Fig. 9 and 10, the FEM stress distributions are simulated for a compressive stress in the matrix, σ_y , corresponding to the onset of yielding. The stress in the X-direction (Fig. 9) is composed of two entities: the transverse compression stress due to the neck geometry and the transverse tensile stress in the vicinity of the interface due to the mismatch of the Poisson's ratios of the matrix and the fibre [8]. In the Z-direction (Fig. 10), the simulation reveals that the maximum interfacial tensile stress achievable with the Broutman test is of the order of 14 MPa, which may be lower than the interfacial transverse strength of many GF/EP systems. At the same time, the longitudinal compressive stress in the glass fibre, $\sigma_{y,F}$, is of the order of 3 GPa, approaching the tensile strength of common glass fibres.

AE failure mechanism separation using parameters from both the time-amplitude domain and the frequency domain allows to determine the physical event having generated the AE signal. In the time domain the discrimination is based on the amplitude and width of AE events. For PAN CF/epoxy systems, the fibre break events have a duration of 5 to 8 ms and a peak amplitude of 25 to 35 dB [9]. For GF systems, the interface debonding event has an amplitude in the 40 to 60 dB range (Fig. 7) with an event width of about 10 ms (Fig 11). The glass fibre break event is characterised by a large amplitude of 75 to 90 dB and a long event width from 15 up to 25 ms; it is usually followed by another large event associated with the slippage of the fibre ends onto one another (Fig. 12) [8]. The fibre/fibre friction following this sequence is generally identified as a repeated pattern, as in Fig. 12 where a pattern of 3 AE events, 1 large event (5-10 ms, 40-60 dB) and 2 small ones is repeated at constant time interval (150 ms), reflecting the 'stick/slip' nature of this phenomenon. All other events occurring during the test, including parasite 'noise on loading' and/or early surface matrix cracking, have event widths of less than 1 ms. Meanwhile, the FFT frequency spectra of the AE events were proved to exhibit characteristic features for specific failure processes and were used as failure mechanism fingerprints (Fig. 13) [9]. The frequency spectrum associated with matrix fracture exhibits peaks in two frequency regions, around 250 kHz and 700 kHz; this event having the highest frequencies. 'Noise on loading' on the over side has a high content in the low frequencies, with intense peaks in the 100 kHz region. Finally, fibre breaking has a wide, dense frequency spectrum from 100 to 300 kHz.

Two categories of thermal residual stresses induced when manufacturing the specimens were distinguished. They were due to (a) volumetric shrinkage of a system in which two materials of different linear thermal expansion coefficients are present or (b) exothermal cure reaction of the matrix system. Thermal stresses due to mechanism (a), affecting only the vicinity of the fibre, were modelled using the FEM. The simulation showed that a compression stress of about 10% of the fibre compressive strength was induced in the fibre while the interface was submitted to a 12 MPa compressive transverse stress (Fig. 14). Accordingly, thermal residual stresses were demonstrated to encourage fibre failure under compressive stresses in the Broutman test and should be minimised when the test is used to study fibre/matrix interface debonding.

CONCLUSIONS

The single fibre Broutman test was originally used to study the fibre/matrix interface debonding behaviour when subjected to a transverse tensile stress. It appeared that two failure mechanisms were in competition in the test and that, depending on the bonding quality, the test could be used either as a compressive fragmentation test providing meaningful information on the shear properties of the interface or as transverse debonding test characterising the transverse properties of the interface. In the compressive fragmentation situation, for PAN CF/epoxy (LY556/HY917/DY070) systems, the average fragment length determined was half of that determined with the conventional tensile fragmentation test. In transverse debonding, for GF/polyester or GF/epoxy (LY5052/HY5052) systems, interfacial transverse strength of 10 to 12 MPa were determined. Thermal residual stresses, determined by FEM, were demonstrated to encourage compressive fragmentation in the Broutman test. For AE failure mechanism separation, the event width was showed to be characteristic of the physical event associated to the AE signal, with fibre break events having a long duration, followed by debonding and friction events. Generally, events in GF systems were longer than those in CF systems. The FFT frequency spectra of the AE waveforms were used as failure mechanism fingerprints allowing to discriminate matrix cracking, fibre breaking, and parasite 'noise on loading'.

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Fig. 1: Principle of the Broutman test.

Fig. 2: Testing procedure for the Broutman test.

Fig. 3: Fragmentation of a PAN HTA5131/Epoxy system.

Fig. 4: Debonded Interface for GF/Polyester system.

Fig. 5: Compressive fragmentation data for HTA PAN-based CF/epoxy systems.

Fig. 6: AE record of a Tenax HTA5131 CF/epoxy system Broutan test.

Fig. 7: AE record of a GF/polyester system Broutman test.

Fig. 8: Progression of the debonding front in a GF/polyester system.

Fig. 9: FEM simulation of the stresses in the cross section.

Fig. 10: FEM simulation of the stresses along the interface.

Fig. 11: Time domain parameters for GF/epoxy system.

Fig. 12: Time domain parameters for GF/epoxy system, post failure region.

Fig. 13: AE spectral fingerprints.

Fig. 14: FEM simulated thermal residual stresses.